

OMICRON VARINAT SENTIMENT ANALYSIS USING NLP TECHNIQUE

G.Akshitha,E.Jagruthi,B.Akhila (Department Of Information Technology)

Abstract- Twitter is a micro-blogging website which provides platform for people to share and express their views about topics, happenings, products and other health issues. Tweets can be classified into different classes based on their relevance with the topic searched. NLP for health-related queries are currently employed in classification of tweets into positive and negative classes based on their sentiments using natural language processing techniques. This paper contains implementation of NLP for message classification based on twitter omicron tweets data set using sentiment140 training data using twitter database and propose a method to improve classification. Use of Lemmatization along with NLP can improve accuracy of classification of tweets, by providing positivity, negativity and objectivity score of words present in tweets. For actual implementation of this system python with NLP and twitter data set are used. In this paper we are using sentiments analysis in twitter tweets for omicron datasets in order to classify the reviews of all users whether it is positive, negative or neutral

Introduction

Twitter is one in all such platform wherever people shares their reviews in brief blogs i.e. in one hundred forty characters. These reviews is for any price like several product or service like moving picture, securities market, schools, colleges, politics and far additional. Here, folks shares the unbiased opinions concerning something they needed, that is why one will take into account these reviews as additional generalized and real one. There ar 5 basic steps concerned to implement this whole system-beginning is choice of coaching knowledge that is chosen on the idea of sort of downside, second step is preprocessing of coaching knowledge which implies removing tangential data like URLs, user names, slang words, symbols etc., third step is to determine reference to twitter learning algorithms like Naive Bayes, Support Vector Machine ar used for the classification of tweets into completely different categories and within the final step results ar displayed on the idea of polarities of tweets when their classification. SentiWordNet2 is lexical resource that is broadly speaking used for opinion mining and it provides sentiment score to every set of WordNet. These score ar of 3 types; quality score, negativity score and judgment score. therefore rather than victimisation Naive Bayes in ancient manner, these scores is taken under consideration in order that additional accuracy is earned. In third section, all theoretical work done is explained like the way to gather resources, their integration and their simulation, in fourth section ancient methodology of classification is compared

with planned methodology of classification victimisation the assistance of SentiWordNet, at the moment future scope, appendix and references ar provided. during this case study, learn the way University Health System leverages Binary Fountain's IP technology Associate in Nursingalyze|to research|to investigate} unstructured survey responses with an accuracy rate larger than ninetieth, turning qualitative knowledge into quantitative business intelligence concerning patient expertise. I. analysis methodology A. System model First, the whole method is roughly divided into 2 major parts: signal process, and emotional coaching recognition. Here, we'd like to require a correct process for the audio signals to get an efficient voice signal at the moment we'd like to alter the options extracted from the voice signals and facial expression from footage. B. Literature Survey A few works are done to diagnose the COVID-19 victimisation machine learning and deep learning frameworks. to notice some, (Narin et al., 2020) propose to use a deep convolutional network-based model referred to as ResNet50 and compare its performance regarding 2 alternative models, specifically InceptionV3 and InceptionResNetV2 for police investigation coronavirus-infected patients victimisation X-ray pictures. Results establish that among these 3, ResNet50 is that the best performing arts model in terms of accuracy. however the dependability of this model is questionable, because it is tested on a quite tiny knowledge set, and its performance has to be discovered on a bigger knowledge set additionally. Another noteworthy study has been performed by Sethy and Behera (2020), wherever they need stacked a support vector machine (SVM) ahead of ResNet50 to sight coronavirus-infected persons victimisation X-ray pictures. A deep learning-based model to sight the sickness from chest CT scans victimisation weak associated an origin Net-inspired model additionally victimisation CT scans to predict the sickness were additionally some recently revealed works on constant topic. Gaining motivation from all the aforesaid works, the planned model aims to attain higher potency standards on a bigger knowledge set in order that it is used for clinical functions.

II. System Requirements

A. Hardware Requirements

- System : Intel(R) Core(TM) i3-7020U CPU @ 2.30GHz
- Hard Disk : 1 TB.
- Input Devices : Keyboard, Mouse
- Ram : 4 GB..

B. Software Requirements

- Operating system : Windows XP/7/10.
- Coding Language : Python
- Tool : Anaconda
- Interface : html flask

I. SYSTEM STUDY

A. FEASIBILITY STUDY

The feasibility of the project is analysed in this phase. During system analysis the feasibility study of proposed system is used.

B. Economical feasibility

This study is used to check the economic impact where system will have on the organization. The amount of fund that the company can pour into the research and development of the system is limited. The expenditures must be justified.

C. TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY

This study is used to check the technical feasibility, that has the technical requirements of the system. Any system developed must not have a high demand on the available technical resources. This will lead to high demands on the available technical resources. This will lead to high demands being placed on the client.

II. EXISTING SYSTEM

The existing work in this area reveals that most of the present work relies on lexical analysis for emotion recognition, that have been used for the purpose of classification of emotions into three categories, ie. Angry, Happy and Neutral. The maximum cross correlation between the discrete time sequences of the audio signals is computed and the highest degree of correlation between the testing audio file and the training audio file is used as an integral parameter for identification of a particular emotion type.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

In the project, MFCC has been used as the feature for classifying the speech data into various emotion categories employing artificial neural networks. The usage of the Neural Networks provides us the advantage of classifying many different types of emotions in a variable length of audio signal in a real time environment. This technique manages to establish a good balance between computational volume and performance accuracy of the real-time processes

IV. ALGORITHM AND MODULES

CNN Algorithm : A Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is a Deep Learning algorithm which can take in an input image, assign importance to various aspects/objects in the

image and be able to differentiate one from the other. The pre-processing required in a CNN is much lower as compared to other classification algorithms. While in primitive methods filters are hand-engineered, with enough training, CNN have the ability to learn these filters/characteristics.

OpenCV: OpenCV is a cross-platform library using which we can develop real-time computer vision applications. It mainly focuses on image processing, video capture and analysis including features like face detection and object detection.

TensorFlow: TensorFlow is a free and open-source software library for machine learning and artificial intelligence. It can be used across a range of tasks but has a particular focus on training and inference of deep neural networks

V. MODULES

A. Add Product details

To build project we have used some sample products image to train product identification models .

B. Train Model

In this Module screen train model generated with 100% accuracy and now show product to web cam.

C. Add/Remove product from basket

a) To allow application to identify product image and then show in text area and if we again show same product then application will remove from text area.

IX .RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

A lot of uncertainties are still present for the best algorithm to classify emotions. Different combinations of emotional features give different emotion detection rate. The researchers are still debating for what features influence the recognition of emotion in speech. A lot of uncertainties are still present for the best algorithm to classify emotions. Different combinations of emotional features give different emotion detection rate. The researchers are still debating for what features influence the recognition of emotion in speech. A lot of uncertainties are still present for the best algorithm to classify emotions. Recent interest in speech emotion recognition research has seen applications in call centre analytics, human machine and human robot interfaces, multimedia retrieval, surveillance tasks, behavioural health informatics, and improved speech recognition. In this study, the overview of SER methods is discussed for extracting audio features from speech sample, various classifier algorithms are explained briefly. Speech Emotion Recognition has a promising future and its accuracy depend upon the emotional speech database, combination of

features extracted from those databases for training the model, types of classification algorithm used to classify the emotions inappropriate emotion class for example(happy, sad, anger, surprise etc.). This study aims to provide a simple guide to the beginner who's carried out their research in the speech emotion recognition.

x. **RESULTS**

Table 1. Percentage Accuracy of Various Algorithms

Naïve Bayes	K Nearest Neighbour	Random Forest
81.4 %	55.30 %	78.65 %

Fig 4: Graph of Accuracy of various Algorithms

Table 2. Mean Absolute Error of Various Algorithms

Naïve Bayes	K Nearest Neighbour	Random Forest
0.2112	0.4475	0.3278

Fig 5: Graph of Mean Absolute Error of Algorithms

Table 3. Mean Absolute Error of Various Algorithms

Naïve Bayes	K-Nearest Neighbour	Random Forest
0.3793	0.6554	0.3925

Fig 6: Graph of Root Mean Squared Error of Algorithms

xii. **ACKNOWLEDGMENT**

The authors would like to thank all our anonymous critics for their feedback on this paper, and our project guide, along with the faculty of Mallareddy Engineering college for women(Autonomous) for their unconditional support.

xiii. **REFERENCES**

[1] Singh, M., Jakhar, A.K. & Pandey, S. Sentiment analysis on the impact of coronavirus in social life using the BERT model. *Soc. Netw. Anal. Min.* 11, 33 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13278-021-00737-z>

[2] International Journal of Computational Intelligence Research ISSN 0973-1873 Volume 16, Number 2 (2020), pp. 87-104 © Research India Publications <https://dx.doi.org/10.37622/IJCIR/16.2.2020.87-104>

[3] Manal Abdulaziz, Alanoud Alotaibi, MashailAlsolamy and AbeerAlabbas, "Topic based Sentiment Analysis for COVID-19 Tweets" *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications(IJACSA)*, 12(1), 2021.<http://dx.doi.org/10.14569/IJACSA.2021.0120172>

[4] T. Vijay, A. Chawla, B. Dhanka and P. Karmakar, "Sentiment Analysis on COVID-19 Twitter Data," 2020 5th IEEE International Conference on Recent Advances and

- Innovations in Engineering (ICRAIE), 2020, pp. 1-7, doi: 10.1109/ICRAIE51050.2020.9358301.
- [5] A. J. Nair, V. G and A. Vinayak, "Comparative study of Twitter Sentiment on COVID - 19 Tweets," 2021 5th International Conference on Computing Methodologies and Communication (ICCMC), 2021, pp. 1773-1778, doi: 10.1109/ICCMC51019.2021.9418320.
- [6] G. Matošević and V. Bevanda, "Sentiment analysis of tweets about COVID-19 disease during pandemic," 2020 43rd International Convention on Information, Communication and Electronic Technology (MIPRO), 2020, pp. 1290-1295, doi: 10.23919/MIPRO48935.2020.9245176.
- [7] Imamah and F. H. Rachman, "Twitter Sentiment Analysis of Covid-19 Using Term Weighting TF-IDF And Logistic Regression," 2020 6th Information Technology International Seminar (ITIS), 2020, pp. 238-242, doi: 10.1109/ITIS50118.2020.9320958.
- [8] "Sentiment Analysis" <https://brand24.com/blog/sentiment-analysis/>
- [9] "Dataset" <https://www.kaggle.com/gpreda/all-covid19-vaccines-tweets>
- [10] A. Pak ,and P. Paroubek, "Twitter as a Corpus for Sentiment Analysis and Opinion Mining," Special Issue of International Journal of Computer Application, France: Universitede Paris-Sud, 2010.